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**The H2020 R&D Project SERENDI-PV:
Innovating towards improved reliability, higher performance and dispatchable grid integration
for photovoltaic systems**

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ABSTRACT: SERENDI-PV project is addressing some of the main concerns which would enable the increase in the penetration of PV generated power on to the European grids. On the one hand the project will address a reduction of the parameters which have the strongest influence on the risk perception for new investments in the sector in order to reduce the Levelized Cost of Energy, mainly associated with the new PV technologies such as bifacial, floating PV and building integrated PV: modelling (better energy yield assessments), faults diagnostics (increase the performance of PV systems), in-field quality control (better reliability), and forecasting. Special focus will be paid on issues that may occur to the PV plants, such as soiling (dust), snow and degradation over the years. On the other hand, the technical challenges and opportunities that will come with the increase of the penetration in the grids, such as the potential of PV to offer ancillary services, etc. will be assessed. Short-term forecasting and nowcasting fleets of distributed PV systems as a whole (aggregation) instead of PV systems alone will also play a key role in higher PV penetration and will be investigated in the project.

Keywords: PV systems, PV reliability, PV performance, grid integration, PV operations & maintenance (O&M).

1 INTRODUCTION – PROJECT RATIONALE

Photovoltaic (PV) energy is expected to play a major role in the generation of electricity in the world, including Europe, and to become one of the major sources of electrical power. However, in order for PV to reach a utility-friendly high-penetration level in the grids in the next decade, two important challenges need to be addressed: (1) To keep **reducing the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCoE) for PV** and (2) to make it possible to **integrate a rapidly increasing share of PV power into the grid**, up to high penetration levels, considering the European ambition to be the first climate neutral continent by 2050 [1].

The reduction of LCoE depends on several factors. The most sensitive parameter is the location (estimated energy yield), followed by the weighted average cost of capital (WACC) [2]. By reducing the WACC the PV industry will be able to convey more trust to the financial sector. The WACC will be reduced by reducing the uncertainties (thus, increasing the trust) in the whole value chain.

First, SERENDI-PV will reduce the uncertainty thanks to the higher accuracy of modelling for the new PV technologies (such as bifacial PV, floating PV and BIPV) allowing better energy yield assessments.

Second, in addition to this, the better-quality controls in the field and in the lab will increase PV project's quality & lifetime and to reduce their performance uncertainty and to improve bankability of the new PV technologies. As a result, higher quality, lower uncertainty and risks in the PV projects will be achieved, what will drive to better bankability.

Third, the uncertainties in the system reliability will be

addressed by applying advanced fault diagnosis in PV plants, with special focus in fault diagnosis in the new technologies, and by using the predictive maintenance of the most complex components in PV system and with the highest impact on energy availability: PV inverter and batteries. This will be achieved by means of a better understanding of potential failures and aging processes of these components allowing to anticipate them.

Fourth, in the same way, the reduction of uncertainties by means of improving PV power forecasting of different PV technologies (bifacial, floating and BIPV) and in case of specific atmospheric events (snow, dust, fog) will be addressed by SERENDI-PV. The new applications such as bifacial PV, floating PV and BIPV will enhance bankability owing to lower values and better traceability of uncertainty on PV energy yields.

In a nutshell, the uncertainty reduction achieved by SERENDI-PV will be achieved through several improvements, including better quality controls, better component and system reliability, and better energy yield assessments.

The second ranked challenge for PV generation is to be able to increase its grid penetration rates to very high levels without compromising the technical and financial feasibility of grids. A first step would be to ensure that PV does not introduce prohibitive costs on the grid management itself. But the actual goal is to bring cost-effective grid management solution provided by PV: grid voltage management through reactive and active power control and grid frequency management by active power control. This can be achieved by controlling PV inverters with reduced costs and efforts by developing standardized smart grid solutions based on the PV data. Another approach is hybridising with energy storage for additional

ancillary services which has the potential to lead to a cost-effective reduction of the grid connection cost. In general, there will be the need for innovative monitoring and management of millions of centralized and distributed power sources to maintain system stability bringing in parallel the opportunity of additional revenues for PV. New revenue streams for PV will in fact be necessary to maintain profitability as further volume growth reduces costs but also exerts pressure on market prices as prices drop when large amounts of zero marginal cost PV are put on the power exchanges. Effective grid management with PV is however only possible if the behaviour of consumers and producers connected to the grid is fully understood, monitored, and forecasted with precision and the combination of PV with energy storage and flexible demand is investigated.

2 THE SERENDI-PV PROJECT: SCIENTIFIC RELEVANCE & INNOVATION GOALS

The SERENDI-PV project proposes innovations on PV systems and their grid integration to improve (1) lifetime, reliability, performance and profitability of PV generation; and (2) high-penetration of the PV generation in the grids with improved stability.

On this basis, the project's aimed leap of knowledge and advance beyond today's state-of-the-art concerns five main "innovation pathways":

1) *Simulation, modelling and designs for better PV reliability, performance and profitability.*

New knowledge and innovations to tackle today's challenges and R&D gaps in four aspects: modelling and mitigation of losses and performance degradation; modelling of emerging PV systems' technologies and configurations (bifacial PV, floating PV and BIPV), solar resource modelling and mitigation of uncertainties; financial risk modelling and mitigation.

2) *Monitoring and image-based fault diagnosis for higher PV performance and optimized O&M.*

Innovative tools and services based on six technical approaches: a) advanced fault diagnosis in large PV plants; b) fault diagnosis in new technologies (bifacial, floating); c) data analytics algorithms for diagnostics of medium/long trend processes d) fault diagnosis in medium and small (residential) size PV plants; e) digital twins for predictive maintenance of the most complex components (PV inverters and batteries) f) improved infrared thermography data analytics.

3) *Quality control (QC) equipment and procedures for PV components and systems reliability.*

Effective quality control throughout the whole supply chain, by innovating and validating testing equipment and procedures for:

- Laboratory facilities, providing indoor quality controls at the component level to address two issues: a) soiling and cleaning on the one hand; b) PV module degradation and failures in the floating environment on the other hand.
- Field testing toolboxes, providing outdoor quality controls at the component and system level, in order to address another two issues: c) soiling and d) PV strings ageing/degradation.
- Quality control procedures for e) PV inverters and f) energy storage, providing a coherent

frame to exploit field and laboratory testing.

4) *Mid-/short-term forecasting up to nowcasting for PV systems aggregations and optimized grid integration.*

- enhanced algorithms for reducing uncertainties of short-term forecasting by merging data from numerical weather prediction models, satellite-based data and recent data from PV power plants for aggregation of individual PV systems to PV portfolios.
- improved algorithms for reducing uncertainties of PV power nowcasting by merging data from sky-camera, from satellite and from on-line measurements of distributed PV systems.
- improved algorithm to reduce or mitigate large forecast errors occurring in case of specific atmospheric events like snowfall, persistent fog, sudden changes of weather, and for higher depositions of dust and higher atmospheric pollution.
- extension of existing PV forecasting tools and models to address PV forecasting needs for bifacial, floating and bifacial PV systems.
- improved algorithms not only for single PV plants but also for aggregated power output of distributed PV systems (spatial averaging of multiple PV systems for different geographic scales).

5) *Innovative business models for PV added revenue at high-penetration levels.*

Novel business models, beyond current state-of-play, for:

- PPAs and energy market integration based on better informed trading services and reduced imbalance costs
- Promoting increased self-consumption for small and medium sized PV in particular by PV-storage combinations or energy supply and consumption matching.
- Aggregated PV in mini-smart grids by combining in locally or regionally PV production with demand and storage solutions with the goal of self-sufficiency or maximisation of collective self-consumption.
- Combined PV and storage to shift PV production to high price moments and increase of self-consumption at household level.
- Ancillary services such as control power and redispatch services to the TSO and DSO.

3 AIMED R&D ACTIVITIES

3.1 PV modelling, data analytics/diagnostics and quality control

The first step towards high PV system reliability and performance concerns the PV system components (e.g. PV modules and inverters). Better technical risk management will address the key factors affecting PV performance. SERENDI-PV will develop solutions at various levels regarding parameters whose influence still needs to be better assessed, such as PV module ageing, soiling and snow deposition.

The project will develop reliable and accurate models to evaluate the yield of PV systems, and especially for new technologies, along with a better estimation of related uncertainties, and their consequences on financial models, at both plant and portfolios levels. The final objective is to integrate this work into commercial solutions. To achieve this, several key actions will be

carried out. The first one will focus on the needs of the industry, and the benchmark of the current tools and models. The actual modelling works will address energy losses which are currently not well evaluated: soiling, snow and degradation. The modelling of new technologies (bifacial, floating and BIPV) will be dealt with particular attention. As an example, an innovative simulation tool is currently being developed for the assessment of the solar irradiance on the back side of bifacial PV modules. This tool will make use of the recent advances in the Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) developed for the video game industry, and that will make it possible to obtain simulation with a high spatial resolution and within simulation times that are low enough to be used in commercial applications [3]. Figure 1 illustrates the application of that tool to the case of bifacial PV modules installed on carports.

Figure 1: Application for PV carports of a novel tool developed at SERENDI-PV for the accurate simulation of bifacial energy gain.

The novel simulation tools will be combined with better evaluation of technical uncertainties and their influence on financial models. These tools will build on previous pioneering developments by some partners of the project [4].

Advanced data analytics will be developed for the diagnosis of the situation (both monitoring-based and image-based) and predictive maintenance of the most complex components in PV system and with the highest impact on energy availability (PV inverter and batteries). These new developments will be integrated in commercial solutions, with advanced and automated functions for data analysis, diagnosis and fault diagnosis (Fig. 2). This will be done both at the Utility-large commercial scale PV plants from SCADA monitoring data, including higher granularity of condition monitoring and specific data analytics for bifacial and floating PV, as well as at medium-size commercial and small-residential scale PV plants from energy meter measurement data and through the development of a BIPV system digital twin. Additionally, the project will develop advanced digital twins for predictive maintenance of the components with the highest complexity, uncertainty and impact on system reliability in current PV plants: inverter and batteries.

Another important focus of the project will be on lab testing facility, on soiling and cleaning; field testing equipment, such as I-V curve tracer; field measurement kit for soiling quantification and improved quality control procedures (QCP) with low uncertainty included for the PV inverter. Several concrete solutions will be developed to deal with key issues that have been identified as particularly relevant in the current state of the art of the PV sector. Such issues are, for example, soiling assessment, with both lab and field configurations, PV modules degradation in the field, through low uncertainty I-V curve

measurements, field quality control of bifacial PV modules, quality control procedures and acceptance tests for bifacial and floating PV installations, field quality control of PV strings, up to 1500 Vdc, floating PV degradation assessment through specific lab testing methodology including analysis of defective PV modules from the, field characterization of inverters and integration with the grid, as well as field characterization of batteries including battery cycle efficiency and state of health (SoH).

Figure 2: Example of image-based diagnostic approaches (CEA-INES) to be further developed and extended in the context of SERENDI-PV, addressing industry-relevant failure modes and new PV technologies (floating PV, bifacial PV and BIPV).

The solar resource will be modelled through a characterisation of long-term trends and a detailed quantification of the uncertainties.

The innovations that are proposed will therefore consider these different typologies, with attention to ground-mounted PV plants, including bifacial PV, floating PV (including off-shore ones), and rooftop residential or commercial PV systems, including BIPV.

3.2 PV power forecasting, grid integration and optimization

The project will aim to reduce the level of uncertainties of the existing services for nowcasting and short-term forecasting. The services developed will focus on a time horizon of intraday and day ahead forecast (time horizons 0 to 48 hours ahead), with adaptive temporal resolution from 1 to 60 minutes. The approach will be developed by merging models based on the use of sky cameras, satellite data and postprocessing of outputs from Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models. PV power production data will be assimilated with models to adapt the forecast for needs of a specific PV system or entire portfolio. The improvements will be evaluated for individual PV plants or portfolios, and in line with the most commonly used statistical characteristics in use in the PV industry.

SERENDI-PV will work towards the improvement of PV power forecasting as input for energy management, trading and grid management by TSOs and DSOs, more specifically:

- Reduction of uncertainties of mid-term forecasting (up to 9 days ahead), short-term forecasting (up to 15 min

- up to 1 day ahead)
- b) Reduction of uncertainties of nowcasting (1 to 30 minutes ahead);
 - c) Forecasting in case of specific atmospheric events (snow, dust, fog)
 - d) Adaptation of new simulation tools developed for new technologies (bifacial and floating PV);
 - e) Spatial averaging effects and enhanced solutions to forecasting of aggregated PV power output at different geographical scales (neighborhoods, cities, distribution grids, grid-nodes, transmission grid, virtual power plants).
 - f) Improving grid stability through smart grid solutions based on PV-data

The energy transition from centralized power supply in the grid through a few hundreds of power plants towards a power supply from millions of distributed energy resources (DERs) is one of the main challenges for the grid operation and a high share of PV. One of the main difficulties is the PV data collection and management as well as the integration of this huge amount of data in the operation of the grid. Therefore, the project will tackle these problems, considering the technical, economical and legal constraints. Based on this analysis, technical solutions for a reliable and standardized IT infrastructure for the PV data, considering high compatibilities for many countries, will be assessed. The discussed PV data and the corresponding IT infrastructure will be utilized to develop and test several technical solutions, including digital twin for the grid, to enable higher PV contribution and a utility friendly integration of it.

3.3 Technical/Economic Bankability, Collaborative platform and New Business Models

WACC reduction is an important pathway towards a decrease in the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCoE) of PV generation, and it needs to be addressed by showing a high level of technical risk management and a more accurate business plan thanks to a better predictive evaluation of the financial flows and financial risk modelling. Some of these points will be addressed in sections presented earlier. This requires a holistic approach in order to achieve global acceptance of 35 years lifetime in bankability, being this one of the factors that most influence the WACC.

In SERENDI-PV, we will investigate on the one hand new business models and on the other we will analyse the economic, regulatory, market design and legal constraints, which are the barriers for the concrete implementation of such models and still strongly member-state specific. For example, it is today in most countries not possible to offer PV-based ancillary services only during daytime blocks, but those are the blocks when PV is both adding stress to the system and when it can contribute to system services.

Moreover, there is a need for a common space which will enable to gather the required knowledge to lower the existing barriers to PV development. Several collaborative platforms have already been proposed in other sectors and more recently in the PV community. Some good examples are PVP/MC/PVlib [5] in the USA, PVGIS [6] for solar radiation, NREL [7] for TMY data on solar radiation, PV performance and consumption data in the USA, or the open source simulation code SISIFO [8] that is the result of the EU projects PV CROPS and MASLOWATEN, or the EU COST Pearl PV project. Nevertheless, there is a need to create a holistic collaborative platform on PV based in Europe, capable of foster knowledge accumulation within the European PV community, and

that focuses on the specificities of PV in Europe, while collaborating with the other existing platforms to join forces as much as possible.

SERENDI-PV will develop an online platform for simulation, design, data analytics, QC and grid integration. This platform will host physics-based and data-driven models and it will evolve to include the needs of the PV sector and new advances in technology. The best experts from the PV community, pertaining to very specialized areas, will be encouraged to bring in their knowledge to help to construct and broaden the capacities of the platform.

The platform will integrate interactive built-in learning tools that will educate the end-user in the best simulation and design practices and will make use of the newest Internet 4.0 digital technology to promote the exchange of these best practices between the PV community members. SERENDI-PV will propose a global methodology for exchanging and storing data to facilitate the integration of PV into the digital era. Sound legal framework is important to transparent and secure collection, processing and dissemination of the data and software tools. SERENDI-PV will draw the inventory of legal aspects related to data distribution and use of software tools, such as terms of use, confidentiality, modes of distribution, and will outline the best practices in the industry.

4 FIRST DELIVERABLES AND OUTLOOK

Over the first 9 months of the project, SERENDI-PV partners have already compiled and worked on the technical/preparatory reports (public and/or internal ones) on the following topics:

- KPIs on state of the art on PV reliability, performance, profitability and grid integration
- Assessment and characterization of the current PV fleet capabilities and regulatory environment for grid integration
- Definition of needs from industry, evaluation of the existing simulation tools and models available on the market
- Revision of state of the art of automatic PV performance supervision systems
- Definition of new needs and specifications on current QC procedures and equipment
- Monitoring guidelines and specific monitoring and validation plan for demonstration of modelling, diagnostics and field testing of large PV plants
- Monitoring guidelines and specific monitoring and validation plan for demonstration of modelling, diagnostics and field testing of medium-commercial and residential PV plants

These reports provide the technical groundwork and define the current regulatory/market landscape (including current industry needs), towards the core development activities on PV modelling, data analytics, diagnostics and forecasting, as well as for the optimal preparation of SERENDI-PV's collaborative platform and demonstrators. The development activities and aimed innovations have a timeline spanning towards years 2022 and 2023. Early innovation developments and key findings on the above aspects will be presented in the next EUPVSEC version.

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